

PRESENT GRAMMATICAL STRUCTURES, MEANING IN CONTEXT AND METHOD OF PPP

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ABSTRACT

This article provides information about the structure of grammar and the use of PPP methodology in teaching English grammar is explained and illustrated with examples.

Nowadays, it is an important task for all language learners and educators, to substantiate while preserving speech forms in presenting grammar. People often call grammar the rules of language, but there are no rules in any language. When we say rules, we mean that someone first created the rules, wrote them, and then spoke in a language like games that use them in speech based on new rules. Some learners, in addition to learning grammar for language learners, that is, without learning grammatical rules, structures, and components, and without consciously applying grammatical rules to the sentence they have created, are self-taught. It is difficult to communicate without grammar rules.

Speech patterns play an important role in presenting grammar. They should be kept in mind when presenting grammar, as students learning a foreign language.

Especially while studying grammar, they should be able to distinguish parts of speech, types, structure, form, location, and other linguistic features of a particular word in sentence. Determining the meaning of individual words or phrases in a sentence, the ability to know the structure of a sentence is important not only in the study of grammar but also in the study of the whole language.

Moreover, while speaking they should pay attention to the pronunciation, stress and intonation. If you pronounce the word incorrectly, the listeners may misunderstand you. That's why stress and intonation play a great role in speaking as grammar rules. Stress refers to the emphasis we place on the syllable of a word or words within a sentence. English makes a variety of use of stress to point to a context. You can ask the same question but can place stress on different words

depending on which fact you would like to have confirmed or denied.

The presentation phase typically consists of two steps: an introductory activity like a lead-in or warm-up activity, planned to raise students' attention in the topic; and an introduction of the target language. For example, if the lesson aims to teach the present continuous arrangements, the lesson could begin with a warmer in which the teacher can elicit a few activities the students enjoy doing at the weekends. Then, the suggested ideas are can be written on the board and the teacher can help with any pronunciation problems which may appear during this step. After all, the teacher can write the students' ideas on the board to present the present continuous. The teacher chooses some of them and talks about his/her arrangements for the weekend. While the teacher presents the new language items, the students just listen. This way, the present continuous can be presented in a contextualized way, which is very important at the presentation stage of the lesson.

Every PPP lesson has a language aim, which students can fulfill by the end of it. Not only can the PPP be applied to teach grammar items, but it can also be used to teach functions, vocabulary, and pronunciation. There are three stages in it: first, the teacher presents the target language; after that, students practice the new language items; and in the end, they use their notes to talk about themselves.

In the practice stage, the focus should be given to the form. The teacher can provide opportunities for students to practice the learned items in a controlled way. This gives a chance for the students to apply what they have learned without making

mistakes. A common controlled activity is a choral drill, in which using the present continuous students repeat the sentences on the board. Afterward, the teacher explains the grammatical use of the new language referring to its function: making future arrangements. Then, a teacher can ask the students conceptual questions to check whether they have understood the use of the language.

For example: 'What are you going to cook for dinner? What about pizza?' etc.

After students have practiced the present continuous, they can use what they have been taught in real-situation-like activities. The production stage focuses on fluency and provides students with a chance to personalize the language learned by doing less controlled tasks by using their ideas. This will help students to learn and practice the knowledge they gained. And I think students must use what they have learned in very communicative tasks. One of the best teaching techniques we can use in the English classroom as a foreign language is eliciting. Eliciting is a range of useful techniques if it is used appropriately. They are used by teachers to get information from students and to get students to come up with vocabulary items, word meanings, ideas, or associations. Still, you need to be careful not to turn your lessons into guessing games, which may be fun but also can be frustrating and counter-productive. When you plan your lesson, you have to decide what can be elicited and you have to make sure you are prepared to do so - be it with pictures or easy explanations.

Eliciting language from the students can help in creating a more learner-centered classroom, getting the students more involved and engaged in the lesson. Rather

than spoon-feeding the students, it makes them more active in the learning process. Eliciting builds according to the students' existing knowledge, linking old and new information.

Eliciting language can take place in many moments during a lesson, for example:

Vocabulary – in a receptive skills lesson (pre-teaching items before reading or listening to a text).

Language focus – eliciting features of meaning, form, and pronunciation of the target language.

General knowledge– finding out what students know, about a topic during a lead-in.

There are a few guidelines for eliciting:

You can use pictures to elicit a particular item, especially if a word lends itself to visual representation. It is the easiest way to use pictures, but you must be careful that your pictures are not ambiguous.

If you want to elicit an action, the most effective way to do it is simply to do it. You can follow up your acting with concept-checking questions to be sure everyone interpreted your actions correctly.

You can use a description if a picture won't work. In this case, describe the word or situation. Moreover, you can use definitions, synonyms, and antonyms to provide a context to try to elicit words or meaning.

Furthermore, there are some techniques for eliciting vocabulary:

Definitions: to giggle- this is when a person laughs in a nervous or silly way; young children might do this.

Exemplification: a gadget -a mobile phone, a tablet, a GPS, an MP3 player, an e-reader

Context/Anecdote: stubborn –(Useful for more abstract items) One of my friends has very strong views and he never changes his opinions, even when it is clear to everyone else that he is wrong; what can we call a person like this?

Mime: to lie- The student lies on the floor

Synonyms: furious -this means the same as very angry

Antonyms: What's the opposite of freezing?– boiling

Flashcards/visuals/drawings/realia:

teacher shows a picture of a lorry, draws one on the board, or brings a toy lorry into class – lorry

Sometimes even with the best of intentions, our students won't know we are trying to elicit and will guess everything except what we are looking for. This is pointless and frustrating for everyone. If your students are struggling to understand your elicitation, give them the answer and move on. Elicitation is a technique that should definitely be a part of your teaching arsenal. And I think, elicitation should be a part of every lesson, so make sure you know how to do it effectively and appropriately.

I sturdily believe that once the lesson is finished and your students have achieved its aim, having been able to produce language in a meaningful way, it means that the method applied was effective and successful, and in that case, the teacher can feel that learning has taken place.

References:

1. Boutte, G. S. (2002). *Resounding Voices: School Experiences of People from Diverse Ethnic Backgrounds*. Boston, MA: Allyn and Bacon.

2. Delgado-Gaitan, C., & Trueba, H. (1991). *Crossing Cultural Borders: Education for Immigrant Families in America*. New York, NY: The Falmer Press.
3. Faltis, C. J. (2000). *Joinfostering: Teaching and Learning in Multilingual Classrooms* (3rd edition). Merrill Prentice Hall.
4. Lynch, E. W., & Hanson, M. J. (1998). *Developing Cross-Cultural Competence: A Guide for Working with Children and Their Families*, Second Edition. Paul Brooks Publishing Co.
5. Hildebrand, V., Phenice, L., Gray, M., & Hines, R. (1999). *Knowing and Serving Diverse Families* (2nd Edition). Prentice Hall.
6. O'Malley, J. M., & O'Malley, M. J. (1996). *Authentic Assessment for English Language Learners*. Pearson Higher Education.
7. Perez, B., & T. L. McCarty. (1997). *Sociocultural Contexts of Language and Literacy*. Lawrence Erlbaum Associates.
8. Sue, D. W., & Sue, D. (1999). *Counseling the Culturally Different: Theory & Practice*. (3rd edition). John Wiley & Sons.